

A NEW APPROACH FOR THE PREDICTION OF THE YOUNG'S MODULI OF PARTICULATE REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A new approach for predicting the Young's moduli of two-phase composites has been developed based on the mean field theory and the topological transformation. The new approach has been applied to Co/WC_p, Al/SiC_p and glass filled epoxy composites. It is shown that the theoretical predictions are in closer agreement with the experimental results than those by both the Hashin and Shtrikmans' bounds and the mean field theory. An advantage of the present approach over the other continuum approaches is that it can predict not only the effect of volume fraction but also the effects of microstructural parameters such as grain shape and phase distribution on the stiffness of composites.

Keywords: composites, Young's modulus, prediction.

1. INTRODUCTION

The search for light alloys of high stiffness has stimulated research in metal matrix composites (MMCs). In contrast to the drastic fall in ductility, large improvements in the stiffness on the unreinforced alloys have been achieved. Therefore, it would appear that the majority of engineering applications will exploit the excellent stiffness rather than the high ultimate tensile strength of MMCs [1]. Thus it is important that the elastic moduli can be predicted. However, the accurate prediction of the elastic moduli of particulate composites is not an easy task for many reasons, such as non-uniform particle distribution and irregular particle shape, which are difficult to include in an exact calculation [2]. In order to predict the elastic constants of a composite body, extreme value theories have been applied. Paul [3] derived a set of bounds (the Paul's bounds) by assuming equal strain for the upper limit and equal stress for the lower limit. Differences calculated by this treatment are normally large, provided the difference in the two moduli is larger than a factor of three. Alternative formulations, involving the variational principles in the linear theory of elasticity, were applied by Hashin and Shtrikman [4,5] to derive the upper and lower bounds (the HS bounds). The calculated bounds provide a closer approximation, since the separation between the HS bounds is much less than that between Paul's bounds for a given volume fraction. It has been realised that the separation between the HS lower and upper bounds is dependent upon the stiffness ratio (E_{β}/E_{α}) of the constituent phases. When E_{β}/E_{α} is large, the bounds are remarkably separated and have limited predictive value [6]. The HS bounds, however, serve as a useful test of the approximate theories, since any theoretical solution outside these bounds is regarded as invalid [6].

Based on Eshelby's continuum transformation theory [7] and the independent inclusion approaches [8,9], Pedersen [10,11] developed the mean field approach to describe the deformation behaviour of inhomogeneous composites. It was found that the mean field approach reproduces HS lower bound and that the HS upper bound can also be obtained by interchanging the elastic constants of the matrix and the reinforcing phase [10]. However, in both the independent inclusion [8,9] and the mean field [10,11] approaches, the interactions between the stress-strain fields of the inclusion particles were not considered. Consequently, these approaches can not be applied to composites with high volume fractions of the second phase. Following Brown and Stobbs' [9] theoretical treatment of the stress-strain field inside and outside a spherical inclusion embedded in an infinite matrix, Fan and Miodownik [12] considered that the interaction between two particles of the same phase should be

small enough to be neglected if the distance between these two particles is large enough. Fan et al [13] also proposed a topological transformation for two-phase microstructures, which offers a solution to the problem of interaction between particles of the same phase [12].

In the present paper, a new approach for predicting the Young's modulus of two-phase composites will be developed based on the mean field theory [11] and the topological transformation [13]. The new approach can solve the interaction problem and can consider the effect of particle shape and distribution on the elastic moduli of the composite materials. The predictions from the present approach will be compared with the experimental results and other theoretical predictions for the Co/WC_p, Al/SiC_p and glass-filled epoxy composites.

2. MICROSTRUCTURAL CHARACTERISATION

Based on the concepts of contiguity [14] and continuous volume [15], Fan et al [13] proposed the further concepts of separation, separated volume, degree of continuity and degree of separation. The combination of such topological parameters can offer a full description of phase distribution in a dual-phase structure. These parameters can be either measured experimentally in a microstructure with any grain size, grain shape and phase distribution using standard metallographic methods, or calculated from the known grain size and volume fraction under the assumption of equiaxed grain and random distribution [13].

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of the topological transformation from microstructure A to Microstructure B [13].

According to the topological transformation proposed by Fan et al [13], a dual-phase microstructure with any grain size, grain shape and phase distribution (Figure 1a) can be topologically transformed into a three-microstructural-element body (the 3-E body), as schematically illustrated in Figure 1b. Element I (EI) consists only of α -grains with an average grain size of d_α and therefore contains only α -grain boundaries. The volume fraction of EI is defined by the continuous volume of the α -phase, $f_{\alpha c}$; Element II (EII) consists only of β -grains with an average grain size of d_β , and with a volume fraction of $f_{\beta c}$ (the continuous volume of the β -phase). Only β -grain boundaries exist in EII; Element III (EIII) consists of the long-range α - β chains, hence, there are only phase boundaries in EIII. The volume fraction of EIII is defined by the degree of separation, F_s . The grain size of EIII is defined by the volume-fraction-weighted-average grain diameter, $d_{\alpha\beta}$, [13]. It has been shown that the transformed 3-E body is mechanically equivalent to the original microstructure along the aligned direction [13,16-19]. Because of this topological transformation, the determination of the mechanical properties of a complicated dual-phase microstructure can be replaced by an analysis of the simpler but equivalent microstructure with three well defined microstructural elements.

3. DEVELOPMENT OF THE APPROACH

It is assumed that a uniaxial stress σ^A ($\sigma^A \leq \sigma_y^c$, where σ_y^c is the yield stress of the composite) is applied along the aligned direction of the 3-E body in Figure 1b. From the strain compatibility requirement, we have

$$e^I = e^{II} = e^{III} = e^c \quad (1)$$

where e^I , e^{II} , e^{III} and e^c are the *in situ* elastic strains in EI, EII, EIII and the whole 3-E body, respectively. For a subsequent elastic strain increment in the whole 3-E body, δe^c , we write the elastic strain increments in EI, EII and EIII as δe^I , δe^{II} , and δe^{III} , respectively. From Equation 1 it is obvious that

$$\delta e^I = \delta e^{II} = \delta e^{III} = \delta e^c \quad (2).$$

According to the virtual work principle

$$\sigma^c \delta e^c = \sigma^I \delta e^I f_{\alpha c} + \sigma^{II} \delta e^{II} f_{\beta c} + \sigma^{III} \delta e^{III} F_s \quad (3)$$

where σ^I , σ^{II} , σ^{III} and σ^c are the *in situ* stresses in the three microstructural elements (I, II and III) and the 3-E body, respectively. Combining Equations 2 and 3 one gets

$$\sigma^c = \sigma^I f_{\alpha c} + \sigma^{II} f_{\beta c} + \sigma^{III} F_s \quad (4).$$

Dividing both sides of Equation 4 by the *in situ* elastic strain in the whole 3-E body (e^c) gives

$$\sigma^c/e^c = (\sigma^I/e^I) f_{\alpha c} + (\sigma^{II}/e^{II}) f_{\beta c} + (\sigma^{III}/e^{III}) F_s \quad (5).$$

Then, applying Hooke's law, Equation 5 is written as

$$E^c = E^I f_{\alpha c} + E^{II} f_{\beta c} + E^{III} F_s \quad (6)$$

where E^I , E^{II} , E^{III} and E^c are the Young's moduli of elements I, II, III and the whole 3-E body, respectively. It is obvious that $E^I = E^\alpha$ and $E^{II} = E^\beta$, where E^α and E^β are the Young's moduli of single α -phase and β -phase materials and can be determined from tests of single phase specimens. Equation 6 relates the Young's modulus of the α - β composite to the Young's modulus of three microstructural elements, while E^{III} can be calculated theoretically.

Since EIII contains only phase boundaries, there is no direct contact between the particles of the same phase, and consequently, interactions between particles of the same phase in EIII can be neglected [12]. Thus the mean field approach [10,11] can be applied to the EIII body in a more rigorous manner. By applying the mean field theory, the following equation can be derived [10,11]

$$G^{III} = \frac{G^\alpha}{1 + \frac{f_{\beta III} D}{(1 - f_{\beta III} \gamma D)}} \quad (7)$$

where
$$D = \frac{G^\alpha - G^\beta}{(G^\beta - G^\alpha)(1 - \gamma) + G^\alpha} \quad (8),$$

$$\gamma = \frac{7 - 5\nu^\alpha}{15(1 - \nu^\alpha)} \quad (9).$$

In Equations 7-9 G^α and G^β are the shear moduli of α -phase and β -phase, G^{III} is the shear modulus of the EIII body, γ is the strain accommodation tensor for a sphere, ν^α is the Poisson's ratio of the matrix.

Once G^{III} is obtained from Equation 7, E^{III} can be calculated from the following equation

$$E^{III} = 2G^{III}(1 + \nu^{III}) \quad (10)$$

where ν^{III} is the Poisson's ratio of the EIII body and it is assumed that $\nu^{III} = \nu^\alpha f_{\alpha III} + \nu^\beta f_{\beta III}$. From the above equations the Young's modulus of the two-phase composite can be calculated.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 Comparison Between the Theoretical Calculations and Experimental Results

In the following section, the new approach developed in the previous sections will be verified by comparing its predictions with those of other theories and the experimental results in the Co/WC_p, the Al/SiC_p and glass-filled epoxy composites. The mechanical properties of the constituent phases in the three composite systems used for all the theoretical calculations are summarised in Table 1. Also listed in Table 1 are the stiffness ratios of the constituent phases in each composite system.

Table 1. The mechanical properties of constituent phases used for all theoretical calculations.

System	Phase	G (GPa)	K (GPa)	E (GPa)	ν	E_{β}/E_{α}
Co/WC _p [3, 21]	Co	80.2	184.2	210.0	0.31	3.3
	WC _p	293.1	381.3	700.0	0.194	
Al/SiC _p [1, 2]	Al	26.1	75	70.0	0.34	6.0
	SiC _p	189.0	181.1	420.7	0.19	
Glass-filled Epoxy [6]	Glass beads	28.7	41.59	70.0	0.22	18.9
	Epoxy	1.33	5.66	3.7	0.39	

For the Co/WC_p composites, the topological parameters required for the calculation can be found in the experimental work of Fischmeister and Exner [20] and Lee and Gurland [15]. Their contiguity data for the WC_p phase (the β -phase) can be expressed as

$$C_{\beta} = f_{\beta}^3 \quad (11)$$

Here it is assumed that the contiguity of Co (α -phase) follows the same trend of variation with the volume fraction of the Co-phase, i.e.,

$$C_{\alpha} = f_{\alpha}^3 \quad (12)$$

The other required parameters can be calculated from the following equations [13]:

$$f_{\alpha c} = C_{\alpha} f_{\alpha} = f_{\alpha}^4 \quad (13)$$

$$f_{\beta c} = C_{\beta} f_{\beta} = f_{\beta}^4 \quad (14)$$

$$F_s = 1 - f_{\alpha c} - f_{\beta c} \quad (15)$$

$$f_{\alpha III} = \frac{f_{\alpha} - f_{\alpha c}}{F_s} \quad (16)$$

$$f_{\beta III} = \frac{f_{\beta} - f_{\beta c}}{F_s} \quad (17)$$

where $f_{\alpha III}$ and $f_{\beta III}$ are the volume fractions of the α - and β -phases in EIII. In general, the continuous volumes of α - and β -phases are assumed to be given by the following equations

$$f_{\alpha c} = f_{\alpha}^m \quad (18)$$

$$f_{\beta c} = f_{\beta}^n \quad (19)$$

The calculated Young's moduli of the Co-WC_p system from the present approach are shown in Figure 2a as a function of the volume fraction of the WC_p phase. Also shown in Figure 2a are the experimental data from a number of investigators [5,21,22,24,25], the results from finite element method (FEM) calculations [23] and the theoretical predictions by HS bounds [4]. Figure 2b shows the high volume fraction region in Figure 2a. In Figures 2a and 2b the theoretical predictions of the present approach are well within the HS bounds. Furthermore, there is a closer agreement between the present theoretical predictions and the experimental results [5,21,22,24,25] especially at high volume fractions of the WC_p phase (Figure 2b) than the theoretical predictions of both the HS bounds and the mean field theory.

For the Al/SiC_p composites, the topological parameters required by the present approach are not available. It will be assumed that, just as in the Co-WC_p system, the continuous volumes of the α - and β -phases are represented by Equations 13-14, respectively, i.e. $m=n=4$ in Equations 18-19. The other required topological parameters can be calculated from Equations 15-17.

A comparison of the Young's moduli of Al/SiC_p composites is made in Figure 3a among the theoretical predictions by the present approach, the HS bounds and the recently reported experimental results [26-31]. Figure 3b shows the predicted Young's moduli of Al/SiC_p composites by the present approach and by the HS bounds over the whole volume fraction range. Figures 3a and 3b indicate that the theoretical predictions by the present approach are in a better agreement with the experimental results than the other two theories.

Figure 2. A comparison of the theoretically predicted Young's moduli of the Co-WC_p system by the present approach with the theoretical predictions by HS upper and lower bounds [4], calculations using finite element method (FEM) [23] and the experimental results [5,21,22,24,25]. (a) a complete WC volume fraction range; (b) high WC_p volume fraction range.

Figure 3. A comparison at low volume fraction of SiC_p among the theoretically predicted Young's moduli of Al/SiC_p composites by the present approach, the theoretical predictions by HS upper and lower bounds [4] and experimental results [26-31]. (a) low SiC_p volume fraction range; (b) a complete SiC_p volume fraction range.

The required topological parameters for the glass beads filled epoxy composites are assumed to follow Equations 13-17. The predicted Young's moduli for graded glass beads filled epoxy composites as a function of volume fraction of glass beads are shown in Figure 4a and compared with the experimental data from Ref. 32-33, as well as with the theoretical predictions by the HS bounds. Figure 4a indicates that the HS lower bound is closer to the experimental data than the predictions by the present approach under the above microstructural condition. However, as we know, in the graded glass bead filled epoxy system the filler normally tends to be much more separated than the matrix. Thus, if the continuous volume of the glass beads is assumed to be 0 ($f_{\beta c}=0$) and that of the α -phase to be $f_{\alpha c}=f_{\alpha}^3$ ($m=3$), the calculated Young's moduli of this system are much closer to the experimental data. A comparison between the predictions of the present approach and of the HS bounds over the whole volume fraction range for this system is shown in Figure 4b.

Furthermore, as shown in Figures 2a, 3b and 4b, the Young's moduli predicted by the present approach are close to the HS lower bound at low volume fractions and approach the HS upper bound

bound to be more closely followed at low volume fractions, whereas the stiffness could approach the upper bound at high volume fractions, as pointed out by Withers [1].

Figure 4. A comparison at low volume fraction of glass beads among the theoretically predicted Young's moduli of glass-filled epoxy composites by the present approach, the theoretical predictions by HS upper and lower bounds [4] and experimental results [32,33]. (a) low glass bead volume fraction; (b) a complete glass bead volume fraction range.

4.2 The Effect of Phase Continuity on the Young's Moduli of the Composites

An advantage of the present approach over the HS bounds and the mean field theory is that it can take into account the microstructural effects on the elastic constants of two-phase composites. Unfortunately, there is no experimentally determined contiguity data available in the literature for the constituent phases of composite materials, thus, it is impossible to compare quantitatively the theoretical predictions with experimental results. However, the predicted effects of phase continuity on the Young's moduli of composite materials do offer some useful information for understanding the composites' elastic behaviour. In the following part of the discussion the effect of phase continuity on the composites' stiffness will be discussed in some detail.

If the continuous volume of the matrix is fixed at a given volume fraction (assume $f_{\alpha c} = f_{\alpha}^4$ i.e., $m=4$ in Equation 18), the effect of the continuity of the reinforcing phase on the Young's modulus can be calculated by varying n in $f_{\beta c} = f_{\beta}^n$ (the smaller n is, the more continuous the reinforcing phase is). The calculated Young's moduli by the present approach at different n values for the Co-WC_p, Al/SiC_p and glass-filled epoxy composites are presented in Figures 5a-5c, respectively. As shown in Figures 5a-5c, at a given volume fraction of the reinforcing phase, the predicted Young's moduli increase with the increasing continuity of the reinforcing phase when the continuity of the matrix phase is kept constant. The predicted Young's moduli reach the Paul's upper bound (the linear law of mixtures) when the reinforcing phase becomes completely continuous and perfectly aligned ($n=1$). In fact, increasing the continuity of the reinforcing phase in particulate composites is equivalent to increasing the aspect ratio in aligned short fibre composites, in which the effect of the fibre aspect ratio on the stiffness of the composites has been investigated intensively. It is well known that the stiffness of the aligned short fibre composites increases with increasing fibre aspect ratio [34]. Furthermore, Figures 5a-5c show that at a fixed volume fraction the increase in composites' stiffness with increasing continuity of the reinforcing phase is dependent upon the stiffness ratio of the constituent phases. The larger the stiffness ratio, the larger the increment in stiffness with increasing continuity of the reinforcing phase at a fixed volume fraction.

Now, the present approach will be applied to predict the composites' Young's moduli in the two extreme cases of microstructure. In the first case, both the matrix and the reinforcing phase are continuous, this is the case of perfectly aligned continuous fibre composite, where $f_{\alpha c} = f_{\alpha}$, $f_{\beta c} = f_{\beta}$ and $F_s = 0$, i.e., $m=n=1$ in Equations 18-19. Equation 6 is now reduced to the classical linear law of mixtures. Therefore, the classical linear law of mixtures is just a specific case of Equation 6. In the second case of extreme microstructure, the reinforcing phase is completely separated, i.e., $C_{\beta}=0$, and the continuous volume of matrix can be changed by varying m in $f_{\alpha c} = f_{\alpha}^m$. Thus, the smaller the m value is, the more continuous the matrix is. The predicted E values by the present approach as a

function of volume fraction of reinforcing phase and the m values are shown in Figures 6a-6c for the Co-WC_p, Al/SiC_p and glass-filled epoxy composites, respectively. In Figures 6a-6c it is shown that at a fixed volume fraction of the reinforcing phase and $f_{\beta c}=0$, the predicted E values of the composite materials increase with decreasing m values. If $m=1$, the material becomes a continuously reinforced composite which has been discussed previously.

Figure 5. The theoretically predicted Young's moduli of (a) Co-WC_p; (b) Al/SiC_p and (c) glass filled epoxy composites by the present approach against volume fraction of the reinforcement, demonstrating the effect of varying continuity of the reinforcing phase (by changing the n value in Equation 19, as indicated in the legend box) on the composite's stiffness when the continuity of the matrix is fixed at a given volume fraction ($m=4$ in Equation 18).

Figure 6. The theoretically predicted Young's moduli of (a) Co-WC_p; (b) Al/SiC_p and (c) glass filled epoxy composites by the present approach against volume fraction of the reinforcement, demonstrating the effect of varying continuity of the reinforcing phase (by changing the m value in Equation 18, as indicated in the legend box) on the composite's stiffness when the continuity of the matrix is fixed at a given volume fraction ($f_{\beta c}=0$).

5. CONCLUDING REMARKS

- (1) A new approach for predicting the Young's modulus of two-phase composites has been developed and has been applied to the Co-WC_p, Al/SiC_p and glass filled epoxy composites;
- (2) The theoretical predictions by the present approach are well within Hashin and Shtrikmans' lower and upper bounds and in closer agreement with the experimental results in the corresponding composite systems than both the HS bounds and the predictions by the mean field theory;
- (3) An advantage of the present approach over the other continuum approaches is that it can predict not only the effect of volume fraction of the reinforcing phase but also the effects of microstructural parameters such as grain shape and phase distribution on the composites' Young's moduli;
- (4) It is shown that the classical linear law of mixtures is just a specific case of the present approach, where the reinforcement is perfectly aligned continuous fibre;
- (5) In the particulate composite systems, the Young's modulus increases with the increasing continuity of the constituent phases. This increase in \bar{E} values is dependent upon the stiffness ratio of reinforcement to matrix. The larger the stiffness ratio, the larger the increment in stiffness with increasing continuity of the reinforcing phase at fixed volume fraction;
- (6) The present approach can provide a simple but effective solution to the problem of interaction between the particles of the same phase.

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